

RELISE

*HARMONY BETWEEN PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL LIFE: EMPLOYEE
SATISFACTION AND PRODUCTIVITY¹*

**HARMONIA ENTRE VIDA PESSOAL E PROFISSIONAL: SATISFAÇÃO E
PRODUTIVIDADE DOS COLABORADORES**

Karislany Lima Barros²

Loys Lane Lima Nascimento³

José Vanderson Cunha Nascimento⁴

Marcelo da Costa Borba⁵

ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the balance between personal and professional life in the corporate context, highlighting the importance of organizational policies that promote employee satisfaction and well-being. As a methodological aspect, a case study was carried out in a company in the building materials and electrical products sector in Parauapebas/PA. The results revealed that although a significant proportion of employees manage to separate their activities effectively, many still face challenges related to workload and the pressures of the work environment. Flexible working hours emerged as a crucial factor in increasing personal satisfaction, with participants expressing the need for adaptations that take into account their individual realities. In addition, the survey identified that pressure at work affects mental health and quality of life, emphasizing the need for actions that promote a supportive environment. Employees also reported that their personal lives enrich their professional performance, indicating that support for the personal dimension can result in greater motivation and productivity. In short, this study highlights the importance of an ongoing commitment on the part of organizations to implement policies that encourage reconciling personal and professional life, with a view not only to retaining talent, but also to improving the organizational climate.

¹ Received on 09/02/2025. Accepted on 05/03/2025. DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19400397

² Universidade Federal Rural da Amazônia. karislanelimabarros@gmail.com

³ Universidade Federal Rural da Amazônia. loysnascimento17@gmail.com

⁴ Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial. vandersoncunha718@gmail.com

⁵ Universidade Federal Rural da Amazônia. marcelodcborba@gmail.com

RELISE

93

Keywords: flexibility at work, scale of activities, professional performance, quality of life, organizational environment.

RESUMO

Este estudo analisa o equilíbrio entre vida pessoal e profissional no contexto corporativo, destacando a relevância de políticas organizacionais que promovam a satisfação e o bem-estar dos colaboradores. Como aspecto metodológico, foi desenvolvido um estudo de caso em uma empresa do setor de materiais de construção e produtos elétricos em Parauapebas/PA. Os resultados revelaram que, embora uma parte significativa dos colaboradores consiga separar suas atividades de forma eficaz, muitos ainda enfrentam desafios relacionados à carga horária e às pressões do ambiente de trabalho. A flexibilidade de horários emergiu como um fator crucial para aumentar a satisfação pessoal, com os participantes expressando a necessidade de adaptações que considerem suas realidades individuais. Além disso, a pesquisa identificou que a pressão no trabalho afeta a saúde mental e a qualidade de vida, enfatizando a necessidade de ações que promovam um ambiente de apoio. Os colaboradores também relataram que suas vidas pessoais enriquecem seu desempenho profissional, indicando que o suporte à dimensão pessoal pode resultar em maior motivação e produtividade. Em suma, este estudo destaca a importância de um compromisso contínuo por parte das organizações em implementar políticas que favoreçam a conciliação entre vida pessoal e profissional, visando não apenas à retenção de talentos, mas também à melhoria do clima organizacional.

Palavras-chave: flexibilidade no trabalho, escala de atividades, desempenho profissional, qualidade de vida, ambiente organizacional.

RELISE

94

INTRODUCTION

The balance between personal and professional life has emerged as a topic of great relevance in the global landscape, marked by increasing demands and constant social and organizational changes (Souza, 2021). The effort to reconcile work responsibilities with individual, family, and leisure needs has become a pressing challenge for millions of workers around the world. Social, economic, and technological transformations in recent decades - such as the advancement of remote work and constant access to communication tools - have extended working hours beyond the physical workplace, encroaching on time reserved for personal life (Novaes et al., 2021).

At the same time, market pressures and the pursuit of competitiveness have led many organizations to demand more and more from their employees, often sacrificing work-life balance in favor of goals and results (Provensi; Silva, 2023). This imbalance has called into question workers' physical and mental health, increasing reports of stress, anxiety, and burnout, and negatively impacting family and social relationships, thereby generating a cycle of dissatisfaction and demotivation (Maia, 2022).

In this context, it becomes essential to understand and seek solutions to promote work-life balance. Organizational policies and practices that encourage flexible working hours, respect for individual boundaries, support for parenthood, and the promotion of employees' physical and emotional well-being are crucial to ensuring healthier and more productive work environments (Santos, 2023). Furthermore, it is fundamental that both companies and workers recognize the importance of this balance and seek alternatives and strategies to achieve it.

A company in the construction materials and electrical products sector located in Parauapebas is the subject of this study, aiming to investigate the impact of work-life balance policies on the satisfaction and well-being of its employees. In the current corporate context, valuing employees' quality of life

RELISE

95

and well-being is crucial for long-term organizational success and sustainability (Predevel et al., 2021).

Therefore, as indicated by Brito et al. (2021), the absence of effective policies may result in adverse consequences, such as increased stress, reduced productivity, and higher rates of absenteeism and turnover (Lima; Júnior; Gomes, 2023). Additionally, companies that do not adopt work-life balance policies face challenges in attracting and retaining high-caliber professionals, as candidates prioritize employers that offer a flexible work environment and support overall well-being (Ferrão, 2023).

Given this scenario, it is crucial to analyze the perceptions of employees in a company in the construction materials and electrical products sector regarding the work-life balance policies adopted. It is important to assess how such policies impact employee satisfaction and well-being, as well as to identify gaps and opportunities for improvement. Thus, the objective of this manuscript is to analyze workplace quality-of-life policies that impact the personal and professional lives of employees in a company in the construction materials and electrical products sector in Parauapebas, Pará.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Zanelli, Borges, and Bastos (2014), motivation is a self-regulated action influenced by biological and cognitive factors that direct individuals toward goals that satisfy their needs, emotions, values, expectations, and objectives. In this sense, a motivated professional seeks to achieve their goals as a result of their needs, desires, and aspirations.

Motivation, therefore, is directly related to job satisfaction. In an attempt to understand the factors that influence satisfaction and dissatisfaction at work, several motivational theories have been developed with the aim of explaining the concepts of professional satisfaction. Defante et al. (2023) highlight that

RELISE

96

satisfaction and motivation are intrinsically related, as motivated individuals tend to be more focused and resilient in pursuing their goals.

Pereira, Passos, and Ribeiro (2022) classify motivation theories into two main categories: content theories and process theories. The former seeks to understand the factors that drive human behavior, with an emphasis on professional achievement. Process theories, in turn, analyze the mechanisms through which motivation is generated and maintained.

Within the context of content theories, Souza (2021) defines them as sources of energy for human behavior, aimed at individual satisfaction. These theories suggest that when a need is met, tensions and discomforts that could lead to frustration are eliminated. Among these theories, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory stand out.

Process theories, on the other hand, recognize that motivation is influenced by circumstances and varies over time. Thus, job satisfaction should be understood as a positive emotional response derived from the perception that the work performed contributes to the fulfillment of an individual's professional values (Oliveira et al., 2020). Unlike content theories, process theories are not concerned with defining what motivation is, but rather with understanding how it manifests and influences human behavior (Souza, 2021).

The Human Needs Theory, proposed by Abraham Maslow, is based on the idea that biological needs are the starting point for an individual's growth and self-development. Maslow presents a hierarchy of needs organized into five levels: physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization needs. According to Vogt and Garcia (2020), the satisfaction of more basic needs is an essential condition for higher-level needs to become motivating.

However, this theory has limitations, as it does not clearly define which needs belong to each level, except for physiological needs, which are universal. This may lead to confusion between needs and values, since different individuals

RELISE

97

perceive their needs differently (Callefi, Teixeira, and Santos, 2021). Despite these limitations, Klein, Pereira, and Lemos (2021) emphasize the relevance of this theory in understanding human behavior and in adapting motivational strategies in the workplace.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory distinguishes the factors that determine job satisfaction into intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors, such as professional achievement and recognition, are responsible for job satisfaction. In contrast, extrinsic factors, such as working conditions, organizational policies, and interpersonal relationships, influence the reduction of dissatisfaction but do not promote satisfaction when present (Tamashiro et al., 2021).

Quality of Work Life (QWL) is also a crucial factor for motivation and job satisfaction. Araújo and Wojciekowski (2023) state that QWL is related to organizational culture, values, and social interactions in the workplace. Monsóres and Novaes (2022) highlight that QWL directly influences employees' commitment and motivation, allowing them greater participation in organizational decision-making.

Fiusa (2023) points out two main approaches to QWL: the assistentialist approach, focused on employee motivation, and the preventive approach, oriented toward organizational norms and culture. Souto (2020) relates QWL to the concept of the World Health Organization (WHO), emphasizing that individuals' perception of their work environment impacts their well-being.

The balance between personal and professional life is another relevant aspect of job satisfaction. Dantas (2023) highlights the need for balance between career, family life, and individual well-being. Luz (2023) emphasizes that this balance is essential for mental and physical health, as well as for the quality of interpersonal relationships. The development of time management and self-care skills is fundamental to facing the challenges of this balance (Pereira et al., 2020).

In this context, organizations play an essential role in implementing policies that promote this balance. Antunes (2023) emphasizes that the effectiveness of these initiatives depends on organizational culture and the ability of companies to respect employees' personal needs without compromising productivity. Thus, the pursuit of work-life balance should be seen as a shared responsibility among individuals, organizations, and society (Franca et al., 2020).

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the proposed objectives, a qualitative research study was conducted, with an exploratory and descriptive nature. The exploratory approach aimed to investigate phenomena that are still not well understood, while the descriptive approach allowed for a detailed analysis of the studied topic, providing an in-depth understanding of the balance between personal and professional life (Assis; Monteiro, 2023).

Regarding methodological procedures, the research was designed as a case study, characterized by direct observation and the recording of behaviors, processes, or phenomena in their real context, without interference or manipulation by the researchers (Sampaio, 2022).

The research universe encompassed the construction materials and electrical products sector in the city of Parauapebas-PA, one of the municipalities with the highest GDP in Brazil. The analyzed company has three units in the city, totaling a workforce of 80 employees. This sector is characterized by intense economic activity and high competitiveness, involving various companies engaged in the production, distribution, and commercialization of essential materials for civil construction and electrical installations.

The sample selection was carried out intentionally, considering that organizational leaders possess a strategic and comprehensive view of the company's operations. As those responsible for implementing policies,

RELISE

99

strategies, and team management, these individuals are in a privileged position to provide relevant insights into workplace dynamics and the balance between personal and professional life. Moreover, their direct involvement in organizational decision-making makes them key figures in understanding organizational culture and the challenges faced by employees.

Data collection included semi-structured interviews, with the aim of capturing employees' perceptions regarding work-life balance. A questionnaire was administered to 20 employees of the studied company, seeking to understand their perceptions of organizational policies related to this balance and their satisfaction in the work environment. In addition, interviews were conducted with two managers and three Human Resources professionals to obtain a deeper understanding of the implementation and impact of these policies within the organization. The analysis of the collected data was conducted using a descriptive approach.

For the analysis of interview responses, the content analysis technique was employed, with the objective of identifying recurring themes, feelings, and perceptions related to work-life balance policies. This analysis enabled the identification of emerging patterns in participants' narratives, providing a deeper contextualization of the quantitative data.

The research results were integrated to provide a holistic understanding of the impact of organizational policies on employee satisfaction and well-being. The interpretation of the findings was carried out in light of existing literature, aiming to highlight significant contributions and practical implications for human resource management. Additionally, recommendations were developed to improve organizational policies. The presentation of results was complemented by graphs, tables, and textual summaries, in order to facilitate data understanding and visualization.

RELISE

100

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first stage of the research focused on the analysis of the respondents' demographic data. It was found that the majority of participants (64.7%) are between 25 and 34 years old, indicating that the study predominantly included young adult professionals. The concentration of respondents in the 18 to 34 age group suggests that the company has a predominantly young workforce, which may influence perceptions and demands regarding work-life balance. According to Aderaldo, Aderaldo, and Lima (2017), young workers, especially those at the beginning of their careers, tend to seek greater flexibility and opportunities for professional development, which constitutes a relevant factor in the analysis of organizational policies.

The distribution of respondents in relation to gender, considering a total of 17 responses, indicates a predominance of women (64.7%) among the research participants. This data suggests that the analyzed group is predominantly female, which may influence perceptions and needs related to work-life balance. Brites (2023) highlights that expectations and challenges associated with this balance may vary according to gender, especially regarding issues related to the division of family and professional responsibilities. Figure 1 presents the distribution of research participants according to their positions within the company.

RELISE

Figure 1 – Position

Source: Research data (2024).

Most of the research participants, representing 41.2% of the responses, are administrative assistants. Next, supervisors accounted for 23.5% of the sample, indicating a significant presence of leadership roles. Managers are also well represented, comprising 17.6% of the responses, which provides relevant insights into the implementation of organizational policies. Additionally, 11.8% of the respondents belong to the Human Resources sector.

The predominance of administrative and supervisory positions suggests that the sample is mostly composed of employees involved in operational and managerial functions. This may indicate that perceptions of work-life balance are influenced by administrative and managerial responsibilities.

Regarding employees' perceptions of the organizational climate, with a specific focus on the harmony between personal life and work, the data analysis reveals predominantly positive perceptions among employees, with 47.1% considering it excellent and 41.2% rating it as good. These results suggest that the organization has been able to promote a favorable environment, facilitating the balance between different spheres of employees' lives, which is essential for well-being and productivity (Maia, 2022). However, the presence of 11.8% of respondents who consider it reasonable indicates that there are specific challenges that still need to be addressed. Therefore, it is essential for the

RELISE

organization to continue providing support and developing policies that reinforce this balance, contributing to employee satisfaction and talent retention (Brito et al., 2021).

Regarding the support provided by the company to help employees deal with personal responsibilities, the data indicate a largely positive scenario. Most respondents (58.8%) stated that the company always provides such support, while 23.5% indicated that it is frequently available. These responses suggest that the organization is attentive to the needs of its employees, promoting a welcoming and collaborative environment, which is fundamental for well-being and productivity (Santos, 2023).

However, the 17.6% who reported that support is provided only occasionally indicate the need to further improve these initiatives, in order to ensure that all employees feel fully supported in their personal responsibilities (Maia, 2022).

Figure 2, which addresses employees' ability to separate work time from personal activities, reveals that although most participants are able to maintain this separation satisfactorily (47.1% most of the time and 35.3% completely), there is still a significant portion that faces difficulties (11.8% sometimes and 5.9% rarely).

Figure 2 – Separation between work time and personal activities

Source: Research data (2024).

RELISE

The analysis of the graph regarding the separation between work time and personal activities reveals that, although most employees maintain a satisfactory division between these spheres, there are areas that require improvement. The proportion of 47.1% of respondents who stated they are able to achieve this separation most of the time, and 35.3% who do so completely effectively, indicates that many employees are managing their routines well.

However, the 11.8% who reported achieving this separation only sometimes and the 5.9% who stated they rarely do so suggest the presence of challenges that may impact well-being and productivity (Provensi; Da Silva, 2023). Therefore, it is crucial for the company to develop and implement additional strategies to support employees in achieving a more effective balance between their professional and personal responsibilities, promoting a healthier and more productive work environment (Maia, 2022).

When analyzing employees' perceptions regarding schedule flexibility and its impact on personal satisfaction, a positive trend is observed. Most respondents (47.1%) believe that flexible working hours can improve their personal satisfaction, while 35.3% strongly agree with this statement. This response indicates that employees recognize the importance of flexibility in achieving work-life balance (Souza, 2021).

On the other hand, the 17.6% who remained neutral signal an area of opportunity for the company, suggesting that there are still employees who may not be fully convinced of the benefits of this practice. Therefore, it is essential for the organization to continue promoting and communicating the advantages of flexible working hours in order to maximize employee satisfaction and engagement (Maia, 2022).

Regarding the level of pressure employees feel in relation to work demands, the data reveal a scenario that, although indicating the presence of pressure, suggests a relatively healthy environment. Most respondents (58.8%)

RELISE

104

reported that they feel pressured sometimes, which suggests that despite certain challenges, pressure is not a constant in their daily routines. Additionally, 29.4% stated that they rarely feel pressured, and 11.8% indicated that they never experience pressure, which may reflect a positive work experience aligned with personal and professional expectations.

This perception aligns with the findings of Santos (2023) and Maia (2022), who emphasize the importance of a work environment that balances challenges and support, contributing to employee well-being and satisfaction. Therefore, although pressure is an inherent part of professional life, the level of comfort reported by a significant portion of employees suggests that the organization is managing its demands effectively.

The analysis of the graph shows that most employees perceive the availability of time to dedicate to family and friends positively. The high percentage of respondents who indicate that they are able to do so “always” (23.5%) and “frequently” (35.3%) suggests that the company’s policies and practices are indeed contributing to a healthy balance between professional and personal life.

On the other hand, the presence of a significant percentage of employees who report having such availability only “sometimes” (29.4%) and a small fraction who state they never have this availability may indicate that there are still challenges to be addressed. These results suggest the need for a more in-depth evaluation of current practices. Thus, although the overall scenario is predominantly positive, the company should continue to implement policies that promote balance and satisfaction in employees’ personal and professional lives.

The analysis of the graph regarding employees’ perceptions of the work environment and the maintenance of an active personal life (Figure 3) reveals encouraging results. The finding that 41.2% of respondents are able to maintain an active personal life most of the time suggests that the organization provides

RELISE

an environment that supports the flexibility needed to balance professional and personal demands. This aligns with the observations of Santos (2023), who emphasize the importance of a work environment that supports personal satisfaction and employee well-being.

Figure 3 – Work environment and active personal life

Source: Research data (2024).

This positive perception indicates that the company's policies and practices may be aligned with employee needs, promoting a culture that values life outside of work. However, it is important to monitor this dynamic and consider that other employees may face difficulties, especially those who do not feel the same freedom. Figure 4 analyzes the difficulty employees have in disconnecting from work after hours:

RELISE

Figure 4 – Disconnecting from work after their shift ends

Source: Research data (2024).

When it comes to employees' difficulty in disengaging from work after working hours, the data reveal a significant concern regarding work-life balance. With 52.9% of respondents indicating that they frequently face this difficulty, it is evident that many employees struggle to disconnect from professional responsibilities, which may negatively impact their personal lives and overall well-being.

This finding aligns with Maia (2022) and Brito et al. (2021), who highlight the risks of work-related pressure extending beyond working hours, compromising employees' quality of life. Additionally, 23.5% of employees reported that they always have difficulty disconnecting from work, reinforcing the need for the organization to review its policies and practices to mitigate this pressure. The presence of 11.8% who face this difficulty sometimes and the same proportion who never experience this issue indicates that, while a minority can establish a clear separation between their obligations, the majority still struggles to achieve this balance.

RELISE

107

Therefore, it is essential for the company to consider strategies to help employees better manage this transition, fostering a work environment that promotes not only productivity but also well-being and personal satisfaction.

The analysis of the company's actions regarding employee well-being indicates a mixed perception of the effectiveness of these initiatives. The finding that 41.2% of respondents rated the actions as good, while another 41.2% classified them as fair, suggests that although there is recognition of the measures implemented, there is still significant room for improvement. Only 17.6% of participants considered the company's actions to be excellent, indicating that satisfaction with these initiatives has not yet been fully achieved.

These results reflect the need for the organization not only to continue investing in well-being policies but also to critically assess the effectiveness of these actions (Santos, 2023). The perception that the actions are only fair may be related to the previously mentioned difficulty in disconnecting from work, reinforcing the idea that policies must be adapted to better meet employees' needs.

The company should seek to understand employees' expectations and perceptions regarding these initiatives in order to develop more effective strategies that promote a truly healthy work environment and prioritize employee well-being.

In the analysis of how employees feel their personal tasks are respected during working hours, the data reveal a positive perception, with 41.2% of respondents stating that they are always able to balance their personal and professional responsibilities effectively. Additionally, 29.4% indicated that their personal tasks are frequently respected, while another 29.4% reported that this occurs only sometimes. These data suggest that, although most employees feel that the company respects their personal needs, there is still a significant portion that faces occasional challenges in maintaining this balance.

RELISE

108

According to Maia (2022), respecting employees' personal demands is essential for well-being and for promoting a healthy work environment, which in turn can positively impact employee satisfaction and productivity. Therefore, the company should continue to strengthen its flexibility and support practices to ensure that all employees feel supported in their personal and professional responsibilities.

Regarding employees' sense of fulfillment in both their work and personal lives, the findings reveal a predominantly positive perspective. With 41.2% of participants stating that they feel fulfilled most of the time, it is evident that a significant portion of the team achieves a good balance between professional and personal accomplishments. Additionally, 35.3% indicated that they feel completely fulfilled, suggesting a satisfactory alignment between their professional and personal lives.

On the other hand, the presence of 23.5% who reported feeling fulfilled only sometimes indicates that this group may be facing challenges in one or both of these spheres, which may affect their well-being and overall satisfaction. This situation is supported by Santos (2023), who emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach to promoting employee well-being.

Therefore, the company should consider additional strategies to identify and support those who feel the need to improve their sense of fulfillment, reinforcing practices that promote both professional and personal development.

The analysis of the graph on the prioritization of leisure activities (Figure 5) indicates that the majority of employees, at 41.2%, rarely consider these activities a priority. This finding suggests that many are dedicating more time to professional or personal responsibilities than to rest and recreation, which may negatively impact their overall well-being and quality of life.

RELISE

Figure 5 – Prioritization of leisure activities

Source: Research data (2024).

In contrast, 23.5% of respondents stated that they always prioritize leisure activities, while an equal proportion (23.5%) indicated that they frequently do so. Additionally, 11.8% mentioned that they prioritize these activities only sometimes. These data reflect the need for critical reflection on the balance between work and leisure. Therefore, it is crucial for the company to implement policies that encourage the prioritization of leisure and self-care, contributing to a healthier and more productive work environment. This approach not only helps improve employee satisfaction but may also result in increased motivation and productivity.

The analysis of the impact of work on personal life reveals that a significant majority of employees, 52.9%, feel that their work frequently affects their personal lives. This perception indicates that professional demands and responsibilities have a notable influence on employees' lives, which may reflect both positive and negative aspects of this relationship. Additionally, 23.5% of respondents indicated that they feel this influence sometimes, while 17.6% reported experiencing it rarely.

These results align with the observations of Santos (2023), who highlight the importance of recognizing how work demands can spill over into employees'

RELISE

personal lives. This situation underscores the need for the company to develop and implement policies that help mitigate the negative effects of this impact, promoting an environment that supports balance between professional and personal spheres. Such an approach not only fosters employee well-being but may also contribute to a healthier and more productive organizational culture.

Employees' motivation to balance their responsibilities (Figure 6) reveals promising results, with 47.1% of respondents stating that they frequently feel motivated to maintain this balance. Additionally, 35.3% reported feeling motivated sometimes, indicating a general predisposition to seek this harmony. However, the 11.8% who reported rarely feeling motivated suggest that this group may be facing more significant difficulties in prioritizing their personal responsibilities in relation to work.

Figure 6 – Motivation for balancing responsibilities

Source: Research data (2024).

These data highlight the importance of organizational policies that encourage employee motivation and proactivity in achieving this balance. Motivation to balance responsibilities is crucial for well-being and job satisfaction, and the company should continue to implement practices that reinforce this sense among employees, preventing personal challenges from being neglected due to professional demands.

The analysis of the graph regarding employees' ability to enjoy their free time without thinking about work (Figure 7) indicates a positive scenario, although there are still areas for improvement. The majority of respondents, at 29.4%, stated that they are always able to enjoy their free time without worrying about professional demands, and 35.3% reported that they can do so frequently. This suggests that a significant portion of employees has been able to establish a separation between work and leisure.

On the other hand, the 23.5% who reported that they are able to enjoy their free time only sometimes and the 11.8% who stated they rarely do so indicate that a considerable portion of the team still faces challenges in this regard. This difficulty in disconnecting from work may negatively impact employees' mental health and quality of life.

Figure 7 – Enjoy free time without thinking about work?

Source: Research data (2024).

Thus, the company should continue to promote an environment that fosters rest and disconnection, perhaps through policies that encourage flexibility and self-care, helping all employees improve their ability to enjoy their free time without work-related pressures.

Regarding the actions and training offered by the company to support the balance between personal life and work, a mixed scenario emerges. Although

RELISE

112

35.3% of respondents stated that the company offers many resources - demonstrating a positive perception of organizational support - it is concerning that an equal proportion (35.3%) believes that only some resources are available. This suggests that, despite ongoing initiatives, they may not be comprehensive enough to fully meet all employees' needs.

Furthermore, the 29.4% of participants who reported that the company offers few resources indicate the need for a critical evaluation and potential strengthening of current policies and practices. The lack of adequate resources may lead to increased stress and dissatisfaction among employees. Therefore, it is essential for the company to invest in more robust actions and training that genuinely help employees manage their responsibilities effectively, contributing to a healthier and more productive work environment.

When analyzing whether employees perceive that their productivity is affected by personal issues, 35.3% of respondents stated that they always feel their productivity is impacted by personal matters. It is evident that this is a reality affecting a considerable portion of the team. Additionally, 29.4% indicated that this influence is felt frequently, while another 29.4% reported that productivity is affected sometimes.

This variability suggests that the impact of personal issues may depend on timing or the nature of the challenges faced, emphasizing the interconnection between personal life and professional performance. The fact that only 5.9% of employees stated they rarely feel this influence, and none reported never being affected, underscores the need for the company to develop policies that not only recognize but also actively address these issues.

The analysis of the relationship between personal life and job performance shows a largely positive perception among employees. A significant 64.7% of respondents stated that their personal life greatly enriches their professional performance, indicating that experiences and satisfaction outside

RELISE

113

the workplace are seen as factors that enhance productivity and engagement. Additionally, 17.6% mentioned that this relationship is quite significant, and 11.8% believe that their personal life contributes moderately to their performance.

These results highlight the importance of maintaining a healthy balance between personal and professional life, emphasizing that a satisfying personal life can be a key driver of job performance. On the other hand, the low proportion (5.9%) who indicated that their personal life contributes little, or nothing suggests that most employees recognize the interconnection between these aspects.

When asked whether employees would like to have more time for their personal activities, the results show that 41.2% of respondents answered yes, indicating that a considerable portion of the team feels the need to dedicate more time to interests and responsibilities outside of work. Additionally, 35.3% stated that they might like more time, 17.6% said that sometimes it would be good to have more time, and only 5.9% of participants indicated they are satisfied with the time available.

Overall, and recalling the analysis of employees' responses regarding work-life balance, the findings reveal the complexity of this issue, which is consistent with the theories of satisfaction and motivation discussed in the theoretical framework. The first response, which highlights harmony between personal and professional spheres, reflects the idea that motivation is driven by a favorable environment in which individual needs are met (Zanelli; Borges; Bastos, 2014).

This synergy suggests that job satisfaction may be a direct consequence of intrinsic motivation, aligning with process theories that emphasize the importance of context and circumstances in individual satisfaction (Oliveira et al., 2020). In contrast, the second response reveals a common challenge: the difficulty of balancing personal responsibilities with working hours. This reality highlights the need for organizational policies that promote flexibility, aligning with

RELISE

114

the concept of Quality of Work Life (QWL) discussed by Araújo and Wojciekowski (2023), which advocates improving working conditions as essential for employee commitment and motivation.

The lack of flexibility may lead to dissatisfaction, as suggested by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which indicates that the absence of motivating factors can result in discontent. The third response, which mentions adaptation to a new work environment, reinforces the idea that organizational support is crucial during transition periods. This aligns with the statements of Aguiar et al. (2023) regarding the need to recognize the diversity of individual experiences. The ability of organizations to provide support and resources to facilitate this adaptation is fundamental to promoting work-life balance.

The analysis of employees' responses demonstrates that work-life balance is a multifaceted issue that requires an integrated approach from organizations to meet individual needs, promoting a work environment that values not only productivity but also employee well-being and satisfaction. This interconnection between theory and practice is essential for the development of effective policies that address contemporary workforce challenges (Gonçalves; Silva; Oliveira, 2020).

The analysis of the collected data reveals a detailed overview of work-life balance among employees of the studied company. The results indicate that most participants perceive a reasonable balance between their professional and personal activities. This perception is supported by the finding that 47.1% of employees stated they are able to separate their responsibilities most of the time, as discussed by Luz (2023), who emphasizes the relevance of this intersection between life spheres.

However, a considerable number of employees, representing 35.3%, stated that they are able to achieve this separation fully effectively. This suggests that a significant portion of the group manages their routines in a way that

RELISE

115

minimizes conflicts between work and personal life. This situation aligns with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, which highlights the importance of meeting fundamental needs to achieve higher levels of satisfaction (Zanelli, Borges, and Bastos, 2014). Thus, when employees' basic needs are respected, their ability to balance life demands increases.

On the other hand, 11.8% of employees reported that they achieve this separation only sometimes. This indicates that these individuals face occasional difficulties in managing balance. The 5.9% who stated they rarely achieve this separation suggest the need for stronger support from the company, reinforcing the idea that organizational practices must be reconsidered to support these employees in their daily routines. This result points to the importance of Quality of Work Life (QWL), as discussed by Araújo and Wojciekowski (2023), who highlight the relationship between employee commitment and the conditions provided by the organization.

Regarding schedule flexibility, 47.1% of respondents agreed that flexibility could improve their satisfaction with personal life. This finding is crucial, as it aligns with Dantas (2023), who emphasizes the importance of policies that promote balance between professional responsibilities and personal demands. The implementation of such policies can be an effective strategy to increase satisfaction and, consequently, employee motivation (Defante et al., 2023).

Additionally, the research revealed that 58.8% of employees feel that the company provides support to deal with their personal responsibilities. This perception is a positive indicator of the organizational practices implemented, as an environment that offers such support tends to increase motivation and job satisfaction. The literature reinforces that the presence of intrinsic motivational factors can lead to increased productivity and overall well-being (Silva et al., 2021).

RELISE

116

However, it is important to note that a significant portion, 41.2%, feels that their productivity is affected by personal problems. This situation highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the issues impacting employees' lives, as suggested by Aguiar et al. (2023), who emphasize the importance of recognizing the diversity of individual experiences and expectations when developing management policies and practices.

The data also show that 29.4% of participants frequently feel pressured by work demands. This is a warning sign, as constant pressure can lead to stress and burnout, directly affecting employee well-being (Antunes, 2023). Therefore, policies that prioritize employees' emotional and mental well-being are essential to mitigate these effects.

Furthermore, 35.3% of participants indicated that they would like to have more time for their personal activities. This response suggests that, although many achieve a certain level of balance, there is still a demand for greater flexibility and free time. The literature indicates that valuing personal time is essential to ensure individual satisfaction and fulfillment (Pereira et al., 2020).

Finally, the collected responses indicate that 64.7% of employees believe that their personal life enriches their work performance. This finding reinforces the positive connection between personal and professional life, aligning with Herzberg's theory, which suggests that intrinsic factors such as personal satisfaction can enhance motivation and performance in the workplace (Silva et al., 2021). This relationship demonstrates that promoting an environment that values employees' personal lives not only improves quality of life but also enhances organizational outcomes.

In conclusion, the research shows that, although there are positive aspects regarding work-life balance within the company studied, there are also areas that require attention and improvement. The adoption of more flexible

RELISE

117

practices and increased institutional support are essential to promote a work environment that fosters balance and, consequently, employee well-being.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

It was observed that, although a significant portion of respondents is able to balance their professional and personal responsibilities, a considerable number of employees face challenges in this regard. This finding highlights not only the importance of organizational policies aimed at promoting employee well-being, but also the need for continuous monitoring of work-related demands. In this way, the goal is to ensure a corporate environment that fosters both employee satisfaction and quality of life.

Furthermore, employees' perceptions regarding schedule flexibility proved to be a determining factor in increasing personal satisfaction. Most participants expressed a desire for greater flexibility, indicating that the ability to adapt work routines to their individual needs has become an increasing priority. This phenomenon reflects a paradigmatic shift in the expectations of contemporary workers, who seek a more meaningful alignment between their professional responsibilities and personal lives. In this sense, it is essential for organizations to pay attention to these demands and consider implementing policies that encourage such flexibility, thereby promoting an organizational culture that values work-life balance.

The research findings indicate that, although many participants are able to manage their activities effectively, there remains a considerable portion of workers who encounter difficulties in this regard. This reality highlights the need for greater attention from management to understand and mitigate the challenges faced by employees.

Schedule flexibility proved to be an essential element for employee satisfaction. Most respondents emphasized that the adoption of more flexible

RELISE

118

policies could significantly contribute to their well-being. This expectation reflects a growing trend among professionals, who seek to adapt their work routines to their individual and family demands, reflecting broader social transformations and new work dynamics.

Additionally, the data indicate that pressure in the organizational environment is a reality for many employees. A significant number of participants reported feeling pressured by daily demands, which may negatively impact their mental health and quality of life. Therefore, it is essential for companies to adopt effective measures to mitigate this pressure, creating a more supportive environment focused on employees' emotional well-being. Promoting an organizational culture that encourages support and understanding is fundamental to minimizing the impacts of stress and work overload.

The results also indicate that many employees perceive that their personal lives contribute positively to their professional performance. This aspect highlights the importance of fostering an organizational culture that values and respects employees' personal dimensions, recognizing that individual fulfillment outside the workplace can translate into greater motivation and productivity. By supporting this intersection between personal and professional life, companies can achieve benefits both in terms of employee satisfaction and improved organizational outcomes.

Finally, the study emphasizes the importance of continuous commitment from organizations in formulating and implementing policies that promote the balance between professional and personal life. This approach not only contributes to improving employees' quality of life but also strengthens organizational culture and positively impacts talent retention. Therefore, it is essential for management to remain open to dialogue with employees, considering their needs and promoting structural changes that enable a more balanced and satisfying work environment.

RELISE

119

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

his research was developed with the technical and intellectual support of the Research Group on Innovation, Business, Organizations, Competitive Advantage and Entrepreneurship (i9).

REFERENCES

Aderaldo, Igor Leal; Aderaldo, Carlos Victor Leal; Lima, Afonso Carneiro. Aspectos críticos do teletrabalho em uma companhia multinacional. Cadernos EBAPE. Br, v. 15, n. spe, p. 511-533, 2017.

Aguiar, Sara Fabiana Bittencourt de et al. O teletrabalho e as mulheres: percepções da conciliação da vida profissional e familiar. Cadernos EBAPE. BR, v. 20, p. 836-850, 2023.

Antunes, Francisco Jorge Arsénio. Políticas de flexibilidade laboral como fonte de vantagem competitiva. Dissertação (Mestrado) – Iscte: Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Lisboa, 2023.

Araujo, Fabiana Pascoal; Wojciekowski, Carla Fabiane. Trabalho ou sofrimento? Estresse do trabalhador da saúde e a importância da qualidade de vida no trabalho. Diaphora, v. 12, n. 1, p. 74-81, 2023.

Assis, Cristina Ferreira; Monteiro, Rhadson. Metodologias qualitativas e quadros de referência para a pesquisa em ciências humanas e sociais aplicadas. Jures, v. 16, n. 29, p. 1-28, 2023

Brites, Cátia Doroteia Nunes Santos. Percepções de equilíbrio entre a vida profissional e pessoal de trabalhadores de diferentes idades [Dissertação de

RELISE

120

mestrado, Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa]. 2023. Disponível em: <http://hdl.handle.net/10071/29948>. Acessado em 20 de out. de 2024.

Brito, Ilzilane Teixeira et al. Qualidade de vida no ambiente de produção industrial. 1ª Edição, Belém: Home Editora, 2021.

Callefi, Jéssica Syrio; Teixeira, Paula Maria Rattis; Santos, Fernando César Almada. Relações entre motivação, satisfação no trabalho e as dimensões competitivas da estratégia de Recursos Humanos no Great Place to Work. Revista Administração em Diálogo-RAD, v. 23, n. 1, p. 106-121, 2021.

Dantas, Bruno Santos. Geração Z: uma análise da qualidade de vida e de aspectos relacionados ao trabalho. 2023. 61 f. Trabalho de Conclusão de Curso (Graduação em Administração) - Departamento de Ciências Administrativas, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, Natal, 2023.

Defante, Lilliane Renata et al. Percepção dos funcionários, qualidade de vida no trabalho e satisfação pessoal: uma análise em uma empresa do setor de processamento de alimentos. International Journal of Scientific Management and Tourism, v. 9, n. 5, p. 3166-3189, 2023.

Ferrão, Inês Seíça. Práticas de gestão de pessoas: impacto no bem-estar, qualidade de vida e desempenho. 2023. Dissertação de Mestrado. Faculdade de Economia da Universidade de Coimbra, Coimbra-Portugal, 2023.

Fiusa, Renato Leite. Qualidade de vida no trabalho: percepção de trabalhadores de um órgão do Poder do Judiciário no Distrito Federal. 2023. 46 f., il. Trabalho

RELISE

121

de Conclusão de Curso (Bacharelado em Administração) — Universidade de Brasília, Brasília, 2023.

Gonçalves, Bruno Henrique; Silva, Fellipe Augusto Lins; Oliveira, João Paulo Leonardo. Qualidade e equilíbrio entre vida pessoal e profissional: Um estudo de caso, sobre o ambiente organizacional. *Brazilian Journal of Development*, v. 7, n. 10, p. 96032-96047, 2021.

Klein, Leander L.; Pereira, Breno Ad; Lemos, Ricardo B. Qualidade de vida no trabalho: parâmetros e avaliação no serviço público. *RAM. Revista de Administração Mackenzie*, v. 20, 2019.

Lima, Lucas Alves de Oliveira; Domingues Junior, Paulo Lourenço; Gomes, Olga Venimar de Oliveira. Saúde mental e esgotamento profissional: um estudo qualitativo sobre os fatores associados à Síndrome de Burnout entre profissionais da saúde. *Boletim de Conjuntura (BOCA)*, v. 16, n. 47, p. 264-283, 2023.

Luz, Jorge Lucas Santos da. As transformações na gestão de pessoas no pós-pandemia e a influência sobre a qualidade de vida dos servidores: a realidade das universidades federais mineiras. 2023. 101 f. Dissertação (Mestrado Profissional em Administração Pública em Rede Nacional) - Universidade Federal de Viçosa, Rio Paranaíba. 2023.

Maia, Aline Passos. Síndrome de Burnout: esgotamento para além da vida laboral. *Direito e Desenvolvimento*, v. 13, n. 2, p. 58-68, 2022.

RELISE

122

Monsores, Geneci Leme; Novaes, Guilherme Lima. Qualidade de vida no trabalho e sua relevância para a produtividade. *Revista Eletrônica TECEN*, v. 15, n. 1, p. 74-80, 2022.

Novaes, Gabrielle Vieira dos Santos et al. A conciliação do trabalho gerencial e vida pessoal de gerentes de uma Instituição Financeira. *Desafio Online*, v. 9, n. 3, 2021.

Oliveira, Aline Pereira et al. Origem e Transformações da Motivação nas Organizações Ao Nível Do Indivíduo E Da Sua Participação No Ambiente De Trabalho: uma revisão bibliográfica. *Revista Vitrine*, v. 1, n. 1, 2020.

Pereira, Ana Rita; Passos, Clotilde; Ribeiro, Célia. A motivação no ambiente de trabalho e o seu efeito no desempenho profissional: um estudo no setor bancário. *Gestão e Desenvolvimento*, n. 30, p. 481-503, 2022.

Pereira, Edson et al. Rede de apoio na conciliação família e trabalho: uma revisão sistemática de literatura. *Psicologia em Revista*, v. 26, n. 2, p. 556-579, 2020.

Provensi, José Augusto; da Silva, Fernando Florentino. Qualidade de vida no trabalho: um estudo em escritórios contábeis da cidade de Porto Alegre. *Revista Gestão, Sustentabilidade e Negócios*, 2023.

Sampaio, Tuane Bazanella. *Metodologia da pesquisa [recurso eletrônico]*. 1. ed. – Santa Maria, RS: UFSM, CTE, UAB, 2022.

RELISE

123

Santos, Clívia Pereira dos. A qualidade de vida no trabalho como uma ferramenta de gestão para o alcance dos objetivos organizacionais. 2023. 66 f. Trabalho de Conclusão de Curso (Bacharelado em Administração) - Centro Universitário Maria Milza, Governador Mangabeira - BA, 2023.

Silva, Rosângela Sarmanto et al. Fatores intrínsecos e extrínsecos: um estudo de caso de uma empresa pertencente à indústria de compensados no Sudeste do Pará. *Amazônia, Organizações e Sustentabilidade (AOS)*, v. 10, n. 1, 2021.

Souto, Clara Nardini. Qualidade de vida e doenças crônicas: possíveis relações. *Brazilian Journal of Health Review*, v. 3, n. 4, p. 8169-8196, 2020.

Souza, Milena Soza de. Como a Qualidade de Vida no Trabalho pode contribuir para a saúde mental dos colaboradores. 2021. 27 folhas. Trabalho de Conclusão de Curso (Graduação em Psicologia) – Faculdade Anhanguera, Pelotas, 2021.

Tamashiro, Helenita R. da Silva et al. Influência das práticas das recompensas organizacionais sobre o comprometimento organizacional, motivação e satisfação no trabalho. *Brazilian Journal of Development*, v. 7, n. 8, p. 76066-76099, 2021.

Vogt, Carine; Garcia, Priscila. Fatores Motivacionais em Indústrias de Confecção e Vestuário. *Revista de Administração Dom Alberto*, v. 7, n. 10, p. 25-59, 2020.

Zanelli, José Carlos; Borges-Andrade, Jairo Eduardo; Bastos, Antonio Virgílio Bittencourt. *Psicologia, organizações e trabalho no Brasil-2*. AMGH Editora, 2014.